

The Oil from the Seeds of *Tectona Grandis* (Teak).

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It is commonly stated in works on Indian Forestry that teak wood contains an oil to which is due its immunity to insect attacks. In some of the books it is stated that the quantity of this oil is so large that it could be used as a substitute for linseed oil. Gamble, for instance, writes that "teak wood is strongly and characteristically scented and containing an oil which is easily perceptible to the touch and is preservative" ("Manual of Indian Timbers", 1922, p. 526). "When quite fresh, teak hardly floats, but when seasoned it floats easily and the oil in the wood prevents its getting water-logged" (*ibid.*, p. 531). He further states that "the durability is probably due to the large amount of oil contained in the wood. This oil is used medicinally as a substitute for linseed oil and as a varnish, but it would seem that its extraction as an oil is difficult, but as a tar comparatively easy" (p. 532). Similar observations have been made by other writers. Vanstone ("Indian Woods in the Raw Materials of Commerce", 1929, Vol. I, p. 380) says that "teak is immune from attacks of white ants and is extremely durable in most climates. When once seasoned it does not warp, split or crack, and is unaffected by contact with iron, owing to the presence of an oil."

From the above it is apparent that considerable confusion exists in forestry literature regarding the oil obtained from teak and the supposed use of 'teak oil' as a substitute for linseed oil would suggest that it is of the nature of a fixed oil. There is practically no reference in chemical literature about the oil obtained either from the wood or from the seeds, except that by Romanis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 51, 868) who failed to extract any essential oil from teak wood. There is no doubt that teak wood is attracted by insect borers (white ants, etc.), to much less extent than other common woods and this immunity is probably due to resinous and tarry matters which Romanis (*loc. cit.*) has reported. It is interesting, therefore, to find out if the seed oil has any constituents that might prove of

value as an insecticide. For this purpose the seed oil has been examined but the results obtained do not appear to indicate any constituent, besides the resin acids, to which the insecticidal value could be attributed. The total oil found to be present in the seeds is 0.23% only, of which 5% are resin acids, the quantity of the acids being small their exact identity could not be established.

The teak seeds used in this investigation were obtained from Burma. They had a hard and tough shell containing 4 to 5 kernels a piece of the size and shape of sesame seeds. Ten seers (20 lbs.) of the seed shells on being crushed yielded 50 g. of the kernels which on extraction with ether produced 20.45 g. of a bright red oil. Thus the oil is 41% of the kernels and 0.23% of the seeds. Steam distillation of the seeds yielded no essential oil but only an insignificant amount of a whitish flocculent matter. The red colour of the oil appears to be due to the colouring matter of the shell. The following are the general characteristics of the oil.

Consistency	Liquid
Colour	Bright red
Sp. gr. at 20°	0.9213
Refractive index at 25	1.4655
Iodine value (Hanus)	107.5
Saponification value	194.5
Hehner value	98.2
Acid value	31.7
Acetyl value	146.1
Unsaponifiable matter	1.25%

Composition of the fatty acids.—10 G. of the mixed acids, from which the unsaponifiable matter had been removed, were separated into the solid and liquid acids by the Twitchell's method with the following results:—

(A)	Acids whose lead salts were insoluble in boiling 95% alcohol in the presence of acetic acid (mostly resin acids)	0.5 g.
(B)	Solid acids	2.5
(C)	Liquid acids	7.0

Chemical constants of the mixed acids.

Mean M. W.	278		
Iodine value (Hanus)	109	Iodine value.	M. W.
Resin acids	5%	30·5	288
Saturated fatty acids	25%	3·8	275
Unsaturated ,, ,,	70%	146	...

The amount of saturated and unsaturated acids being small, attempts were not made to separate and identify the individual acids by their fractional crystallisations or the fractional distillation of their methyl esters. In the case of liquid acids it was found that on standing the iodine value fell from 146 to 63, making the acids viscous and much less soluble in petroleum ether. The data recorded above appear to indicate that the solid acid portion consists mainly of stearic and palmitic acids and the liquid acid portion consists mainly of oleic and linoleic acids.

